

Effects of Social Networking Sites on Students

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the impact of Social Networking Sites on the students which is based on secondary data taken from various studies done by different researchers in the context of change in behavior patterns and academic performance of students due to the use of social networking sites. Now a days social networking sites has become popular among students and they gets effected by excessively using it. There is need to take some steps to saved students from adverse effects of using social networking sites. The findings of the below study revealed that on the one side social networking sites is boon for students because they using it for enhancing their knowledge, for connecting friends and teachers etc. but on the other side social networking sites adversely effected their studies causing lower grades, loss of concentration, time wastage promoting grammerly errors while chatting and class buncking etc. Parents should keep on watch their children's online activities so that they remain safe by using social networking sites and dont waste their precious time on useless activities.

Keywords: Social networking sites, academic performance, adversely, concentration, buncking, activities.

1. Introduction

Social networking sites have been seen as a important tools in the modern era. This is all because of the enormous importance associated with it. Teachers can share their learning content on it and pass their ideas and share it with students at the same time students also learn with the help of social networks and can use their precious time with learning.

In general, students are the group who are more interested in using modern technology in every field compare to any other age group.

Social networking sites have abilities of promoting virtual communities to interact and communicate synchronously or asynchronously (Fogel & Nehmad, 2009). Page | 2

It is important to understand that Social Media is a very broad term and social networking sites are one of the popular forms of social media (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

Boyd and Ellison define Social networking site as "Web based sites that allows individuals to (i) construct a public and semi- public profile within a bounded system (ii) articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection and (iii) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from one social networking sites to another site".

Social networking sites is an umbrella term used for social media and it includes not only Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, MySpace. Social media is internet based technologies that allow free flowing communication among the users.

However, despite the advantage of social networking sites, it has been observed that the excessive usage of social networking sites by students effected their studies and also effected them mentally and physically. For instance, Olubiyi (2012) noted that students are so engrossed in the social media and spend a great deal of time online. Even in classrooms and lecture theaters, it has been observed that some students are always busy in using Facebook while lectures are on (Olubiyi, 2012). Students time which ought to have been channeled towards

learning, academic research and innovative ventures have been crushed by the passion for meeting new friends online and most times busy in discussing trivial issues (Olubiyi, 2012).

So we can say that social networking sites is useful when we use it carefully and only for the purpose of updating yourself about current issues and learning which is helpful in enhancing students academic performance then we can say social networking sites is boon for students otherwise excessive use of social networking sites is time consuming and not good for their mental as well as physical health.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. 'Positive Effects of Social Networking sites on Students'

Wheeler (2007), Rifkin, Longnecker, Leach, and Ortia (2009) studies indicated that social media bring some major advantage for students. These include: enhancing relationship, learning motivation improvement, offering personalised course material, and developing collaborative abilities. Social networking sites enhances relationships because through social networking sites a lot of former schoolmates have reunited.

Many students using social networking sites like Facebook, Whatsapp, Telegram to communicate with each other. A lot of students taking help with these sites for learning purposes they exchange course materials on these sites. Most of the students download course material on the internet and send them to their friends.

Researchers have found positive outcomes in online community engagement among students. Tienne (2000, p.89) proved that "written communication in cyberspace enables students to take part in discussions at a time convenient to them and articulate their ideas in more carefully and structured ways".

Deng and Tavares (2013) also posit that "Web-based discussions among students can contribute to the students' reflective ability and critical thinking skills." The authors added that with relative face-to-face communication, "students are more willing to voice their views (agreements or disagreements) and more attuned to others' opinions in online discussions.

Badawy and Hashem (2015) in their study on the 'Impact of social media on Academic development of school students' found the influence of social media on academics study of students. Facebook and emails were used as a platform for the collection of data through Questionnaire among 110 male and 110 female students aged 12-19, which are in grades 7th to 12th and likert scale was used for the analysis of data collected to find out the frequency of usage by students. The data revealed that student's academics was not influenced by social media in any way because although they spend hours on social media, they still manage to find time to study and achieve grades.

Hussain , Mahmood and Rasool (2016) in their work on 'A comparative study between the learning style of user and non-user students of social media at Elementary school level' made a comparison at Lahore city through Simple Random sampling technique collected the data from 100 users and 100 non users of social media. The data statistically analyzed and concluded that social media doesn't have any significant role in terms of student's negligence towards studies even it was found more efficient for students using social media in finding matters related to study and getting in touch for group studies as comparison to non-users of social media.

Patel (2011) in his research 'Comparative study and analysis of social networking sites' compared the two most commonly used social networking sites i.e. Facebook and LinkedIn. Survey was officially conducted with the approval from Institutional Review Board among the

target audience. The study states that both carries an important part in today's world as Facebook helps in building relationship and making new friends whereas LinkedIn helps in connecting with professionals and getting a vast exposure to the social world.

Bicen and Cavus (2011) in their study 'Social network sites usage habits of undergraduate students' investigated the usage of Facebook among the students in the department of Computer Education and Instructional Technologies (CEIT) in Northern Cyprus. Eighty six undergraduate students participated in the present study. Data was collected by means of online survey developed by researchers and was analyzed using SPSS program with percentage, frequency and mean statistical analysis technique. The study revealed that students spend a significant amount of their time using Facebook. Students also increase their knowledge and communication skills by sharing photographs, links that they like, and news with their friends. The scholar suggested that future studies should concentrate on integrating the Facebook into education and teaching, which is important in students' everyday working lives.

Ahn (2011, p.237) adds that "Social Media provides a platform for youth or students to participate in communities that help them to learn and also practise skills within a particular knowledge area."

By spending so much time with new technologies, students develop more familiarity with computers and other electronic devices. With the increased focus on technology in education and business, this will help students build skills that will help them throughout their lives. (Dunn, 2011).

Teens are more likely to say social media makes them feel more included and confident rather than excluded or insecure

% of U.S. teens who say that social media makes them feel more ...

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Note: Respondents who did not give an answer are not shown.

Source: Survey conducted March 7–April 10, 2018.

"Teens' Social Media Habits and Experiences"

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2.2. 'Negative Effects of Social Networking Sites on Students'

Several studies have shown that social networking sites effects students academic performance and shows negative correlation between social networking sites and students academic achievement.

According to Malaney (2005), the internet and social media networks have a negative impact on pupils' grades. According to Banquil et al. (2009), students' grades have been declining due to their use of social media. These studies show that social media has an academic impact on kids.

American Educational Research Association 2009 annual conference stated that the United States College students have lower grades because they use Social Networking Sites extensively.

As per the research of Kuppuswamy and Shankar (2010) Online social networking sites distract students to non- academic usage and unnecessary actions, including useless discussion.

Choney (2010) in his research concluded that Facebook users have lower Grade Point Average in compare of non users of Facebook.

Reynol Junco (2012) revealed that spending time on Facebook as well as time spent to check Facebook were adversely linked to the overall academic grades of students in terms of GPA. Haq and Chand (2013) in their study concluded that Facebook adversely influence academic performance of students. The study further noticed that male and females spend equal time on internet where females used Facebook more, but males had more friends than females. Facebook use had adverse effects on males than females because males spend more time on sport and games activities which caused a loss of time and negative influence on his performance.

Several students in Oman stated that their language patterns had changed due to regular communication on their social networks, according to Mehmood and Taswir (2013). This highlights how damaging social media can be to a student's ability to communicate. As per the research of Legaree (2015) excessive usage of social media can stress students and affect their academic performance.

Bhatt and Arshad (2016) in their study 'Impact of Whatsapp on youth' examined the intensity of the usage of whatsapp and its effect on education and family of the youth of Agra region. Survey was conducted among randomly selected whatsapp users with sample size of 100 peoples between age group of 17 to 30 years. The study reveals that whatsapp is a major cause for social isolation as it promotes only virtual relationship instead of real relationship. In term

of education also it had a negative impact on people as it encourages the grammatical mistakes, errors in sentence construction, lecture bunking, etc.

Sharma and Shukla (2016) concluded that Whatsapp affected Indian student's academic language and promoting grammatical errors and wrong sentence formation between them. Students may get deceptive and fake information. They spend lot of time on this application rather than spending quality time with their family members.

Masthi and Mallekavu (2017) in their study 'A comparative study on social media addiction between public and private high school of urban Bengaluru, India' investigated the level of addiction of social media between private and public high schools. Cross sectional study was conducted in both schools using random sampling method Questionnaire was distributed among the students of age 12 to 16 years. Total of 760 subjects were studies from both the schools. Psychological and behavioral problem were observed among the users of private schools students and they were found more susceptible for social media addiction. A multitude of physical, psychological and behavior problems were observed among private schools social media uses.

3. Objectives

- 1.To Analyze the Positive effect of social networking sites on students.
2. To Analyze the Negative effect of social networking sites on students.
3. To Analyze the effect of social networking sites on academic performance of students.

3.1. Methodology

In sight came from analysis of various studies related to positive and negative effect of social networking sites on students. Present study is based on secondary data taken from different studies related to change in behaviour of students as well as in their academic performance.

4. Conclusion

Social networking sites have both aspects positive and negative. On the one hand it is boon for students if they enhancing their knowledge with the help of social networking sites and it's bane for them when they excessively indulge in social networking sites which effects their studies getting lower grades, class bunning, loss of concentration etc. It is always advised that the parents should keep eyes on their children's online activities. So that they did not indulge in those activities which is not beneficial for them and do effect their academic performance. Students are the future of any country if they do waste their precious time in excessively using social networking sites which is effected for their physical as well as mental health then country's development is at stake. So at the end we can only said that social networking sites usage should be limited and its usage is to turned in to the positive way then only society would develop.

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